

Transcription of Interview 10

October 2020

Shane: What are your views on the National Health Insurance?

Interview 10: My views on the National Health Insurance, I would say, I think it's something that should be welcomed in the country. If we look at the state of, both, the public and the private health facilities, I think, contrary to a popular belief that private health facilities are way better than public, as a user of private, I can tell you, that that is not exactly true. So I think it is something that the country should be working towards, seeing the current economic conditions that we are being faced with, that, in fact, it has become unaffordable for government to continue in the manner in which we are. So personally, it's something that I am looking forward to. I have had experience of family members of mine in South Korea, for example, who have used their public health facilities, because they are on a similar kind of model, and the feedback that I've got, is that it actually works. So, Shane, I'm hoping that that is answering your question.

Shane: Yes. And with regards to the NHI Papers and the Bill, what is your view on the structure, and the outline of that?

Interview 10: I haven't looked at them in detail. I have looked at some of their documents. I have attended one or two of their workshops on NHI, but at a very high level; so I personally have not gone into detail, into the Bills that have been issued.

Shane: Okay.

Interview 10: So since I come from an accounting background, I think I was more interested in the cost and how the funding model is going to work, etc.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to that, what is your engagement with the NHI policy development? Have you been engaged, or worked with the financial aspects?

Interview 10: No, I have not.

Shane: Okay. And as you are aware, do you know that what means government has been using to engage with managers, both national, provincial, and district?

Interview 10: I'm not sure what other managers have attended, but there was one meeting that I attended, with the previous MEC, MEC Masuku, where it was more like a community engagement; so that is one of the meetings that I've attended as a senior manager in the department. So we were forming part of that community engagement, that MEC Masuku had.

Shane: Okay. And currently, the information and the feedback loop on the NHI, do you receive something like that? Or how do you get most of your information about the NHI?

Interview 10: We have not been receiving information on the NHI, so it's basically what you would go and read up on. But as senior managers, I don't think that we have been kept abreast in terms of what is

going on. I used to work at the provincial office, until about a year ago, so I've just joined the district office last September.

Shane: Okay.

Interview 10: But even when we were in the province, at least in some of our strategic meetings, NHI would be a discussion; but at district level, I must say, it is very silent. Since I've been at the district, I've never heard them discuss NHI on any platform.

Shane: Sjoe! Why do you think that is?

Interview 10: Okay, let me not use covid as an excuse, because I'm not sure whether covid has taken over some of these events. But really, I would not know why the department is not giving it the attention that it needs. But like I said, when I used to work at the provincial office, it used to form part of our strategic agendas, but in terms of the district, we have never discussed it at any meeting; and the reasons for that, really, I would not know what the reasons are.

Shane: Okay.

[05:00]

Interview 10: And I think one of the other things that I've picked up, when I first came to the district, I don't think the managers in the district are really aware of what is going on with NHI. There was a time when I tried to arrange, with Dr Adiel, for him to come and brief the managers in one of our EXCO meetings, but that meeting did not materialise. So personally, I think I will just try and take it up again with him.

Shane: Okay. And then our third question is, about the current implementation of the NHI, what is your perception of that? Are we ready for it? Is it on the go?

Interview 10: I would say, if you look at the current economic situation, I think we could not be ready. I think this is an opportune time for us to really fast-track the implementation of NHI. I think the current economic situation demands that we start to look at provision of health services, differently. Because if we have to continue the way we are continuing at the moment, our health services will sooner or later collapse. If you have to look at the amount of litigation that we, as the health department, not only in Gauteng, but throughout the country, if you have to look at the litigation costs that currently, we are liable for, if at any point in time, if those amounts are demanded, you will literally see a collapse of the entire health system.

Shane: Sjoe!

Interview 10: So my view is that, now, is the perfect time.. seeing how difficult things are in the country, I think, now, is the perfect time for us to have something like this.

Shane: Do you think that the NHI would remediate that, or take away some of the burden?

Interview 10: I think it would take away some of the burden, especially if you look at what happens to patients that do have health insurance at this point in time; but you know, that the moment their health insurance is exhausted, then they become a patient at a public health facility.

Shane: Yes.

Interview 10: So I think it will help us, if we could just look at that now.

Shane: Okay. And do you think that there would be less litigation, or do you think the person that's being litigated is no longer state, per say?

Interview 10: I would be wary to say that there would be less litigation, because I think the root causes of litigation has to be addressed, whether we are on NHI or not. So I would be wary to say that the litigation would be reduced, but I am hoping that some of the skills that are, both, in public and private, that if those skills are merged and we can look at how private deals with matters of their litigation, then maybe we can have a way forward.

Shane: So like a collaborative sort of sharing?

Interview 10: Yes. Because I mean, if you look at the manner in which the state is litigated, it is not very often that I've heard of huge scale litigation in private; I know that there is, but I'm sure there are ways and means that they have got, in terms of dealing with it.

Shane: Yes. And with regards to the current public infrastructure and services, do you believe that they're in a state.. ready to implement NHI?

Interview 10: In terms of infrastructure, I think a lot has been done, in terms of improving infrastructure, but I don't think we are there yet. Because I know for a fact, that many of our facilities, they're still having a lot of infrastructure challenges. So I'm hoping that even with the introduction of NHI, we will continue to build on our facilities. And one of the things that I would like to see happening, is for us to continue to maintain the facilities that we currently have, instead of continuously looking at building new facilities. I think we should focus more on.. because I think if we continue to build, but we are not maintaining, that, for me, is a problem. So I would rather they focus on bringing facilities up to standard, instead of just continuing to come up with new facilities, whilst ignoring those that we currently have.

[10:31]

Shane: Okay. And with regards to the implementation, what do you think would be necessary, or what do you think would help us to get everything aligned and on the roll?

Interview 10: I think they would need to look at the various roleplayers; it would have to really be, I think, in terms of the public, or citizens of the country, seeing NHI for the value that it may bring. I don't think much has been done about that; because really, I mean, in recent times, it has been very, very quiet, regarding NHI. So I'm not sure what government's plans are, to make sure that citizens understand what is it that they are trying to do with NHI, because I think, perceptions are overtaking; people's perceptions of what NHI is going to do, is really not what should be out there. So I don't know

what government's plans are, in terms of making sure that citizens understand it, they buy into it. So for me, that would be a huge thing, because if people don't buy into the idea, we may find ourselves backtracking on some of the decisions that we have made. And then, of course, the condition of the facilities, and our staff, of course, because that **means** staff are going to play an important role in the entire NHI implementation; so if they don't understand it, and if they don't support it, I think we are going to have a problem.

Shane: Okay. And are there any other challenges that you could see at a provincial or district level, that could block the successful, smooth implementation of NHI?

Interview 10: I think the people issues, for me, could be one of the biggest challenges; and then, of course, the Bill that would need to be refined, if necessary. And I know that the Ministry was supposed to set up what they call an NHI implementation office, so that they [..], **therefore**, the introduction of the fund; I'm not sure if that has been done. But I think some of the key things, would be the filling of vacant posts, because if we continue to have vacant posts, we are going to be backtracking on some of our key interventions. And then, improving and maintaining, I would say, our hospital, as well as the clinics, their infrastructure. Then the access to medicine, to equipment, all our medical products; I think those, for me, would be some of the key things that would have to be in place. So your medication, your products, your equipment, equipment that has to be maintained, not just lying.. continuously buying new equipment, whilst we have equipment lying around.

Shane: Yes. And with regards to the operationalisation, and so the funding and the bureaucratic processes, what is your view on that structure, and the rollout of NHI?

Interview 10: Just explain what exactly you're looking for this?

Shane: So from government and the NHI fund, and then establishing a fund that is separate from a purchaser and providers split, and that purchasing mechanism to purchase services from the primary care sector; do you have any views or opinions on that, or experience with it?

Interview 10: Well, I'm hoping that it will give us more purchasing power. We may also benefit from the economies of scale; even though, now, I mean, public, we are still the largest buyer, in terms of your medical equipment, etc., I don't think that we are being treated fairly, in the markets.

[15:07]

So one of the things that may help us, is that we may be able to use knowledge-base of privates, to help us about those things, because I firmly believe that we are really not treated fairly by the private sector. I mean, some of the equipment that the private sector would manufacture, for example, if government does not buy that piece of equipment, then they don't have a market for it.

Shane: Okay. Okay, Mrs Interview 10, my last question is just, broadly, if there's any other view or thought that you would like to express on the NHI?

Interview 10: I think my only other view would be, I think it would be a huge disappointment if the fund is not managed appropriately, because if we are going to go this route, and we are saying that the

fund is going to be the driver of the provision of health services in the country, if that fund is not going to be managed in the right manner, that the money that goes through there, is really used for healthcare services, I think that, for me, will be a huge disappointment. So ideally, every cent that gets into the NHI fund, must find its way back into healthcare services; that, for me, would be the cherry on the top.

Shane: Okay, then that's all from my side, not too long at all. But then thank you so much for your time, and..

Interview 10: I hope that that's of value to you.

Shane: Definitely, ja, definitely financial aspect and seeing things, and the link between provincial and district, definitely clarified.

Interview 10: Ja, and I think in the issue of the ideal clinics, and all of that, we would still need to continue with that, so that our clinics.. we don't only worry about the hospitals, and your bigger facilities, and that the clinics also be given the necessary attention, because even with NHI, if services are then going to be provided at the wrong levels of care, we are so going to have a problem. So if our clinics are really what they're supposed to be, people will want to go there, and then, of course, then, once they start receiving treatment at the correct levels of care, you will find that it will also have an impact on us, financially, but a positive impact.

Shane: Okay.

Interview 10: So I think the attention to primary healthcare, still remains key, for us to make any intervention a success.

Shane: Okay, perfect. Thanks Mrs Interview 10, thanks so much for your time, and also for your support with the emails and..

Interview 10: If there's anything else, you can just email me.

Shane: Yes, I'll also send you a transcript of the interview, so you can just review, and if there's anything you'd like to change or add, you could do so.

Interview 10: That's fine, okay. Thank you so much.

Shane: Thanks so much. Bye.

Interview 10: Bye-bye.

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